

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Redl****FIRST NAME: Nina****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MS Word 365, Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What are the four crucial stages of any writing process?**

- Prewriting, writing, revising, editing.¹**
- Research, writing, publication, oral presentation.
- Drafting, writing, further research, publication.
- Writing, editing, new draft, second stage of writing.

2. **Every good argument includes which elements?**

- Observation, example, exception, conclusion.
- Introduction, opinion, example, conclusion.
- Opinion, qualifier, research component, concession.
- Opinion, qualifier, support, concession.²**

¹ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000. A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington, Massachusetts: Great Source Publishing Group, 1999), 104.

² *Ibid.*, 122.

3. **In research, most well-designed experiments accomplish what?**
- They yield the expected results.
 - They can be interpreted according to one's needs.
 - They end up supporting the null-hypothesis.³**
 - They produce final results that need no further explanation.
4. **Irrelevant information for a research paper includes which of the following?**
- Extensive referencing of other studies.
 - Anecdotal information and superlatives.⁴**
 - Several graphs and tables.
 - Extensive details on the research methodology.
5. **When writing according to the WHO Style Guide, how are dates formatted? (pay attention to the punctuation or lack thereof presented in each possible answer)**
- Day Month (spelled out in full) Year.⁵**
 - Day/Month (abbreviated)/Year.
 - Month (number)/Day/Year.
 - Day Month, Year.
6. **How should numbers be written when they are part of the text (not as part of a citation)?**

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 11.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 6-7.

⁵ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 7.

- Numbers less than 10 are spelled out. Numbers 10 and higher are written in figures unless used in a specific numerical context or a series of numbers.**⁶
- All numbers are written in figures.
- All numbers are spelled out unless used in a specific numerical context or a series of numbers.
- Numbers are written in either numbers or figures depending on what audience one writes for (e.g., numbers in scientific research papers are always written in figures).
7. **In the Turabian Author-Date citation style, books by a single author are referenced with which of the following formula? (pay attention to the punctuation or lack thereof presented in each possible answer)**
- Author's first name Author's last name. Edition. Date. Title (underlined). Editor(s)/Translator(s). Place: Publication Press.
- Author's last name, Author's first name, Edition (if existing). Date. Title (italics). Editor(s)/Translator(s) (if existing). Place: Publication Press.**⁷
- Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (in parentheses), Title, Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.
- Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (in parentheses), Title (in quotation marks), Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.
8. **In the Turabian Author-Date citation style, if a publication has several authors, how are they correctly referenced regarding their first and last names?**
- The names of all authors are inverted.

⁶ World Health Organization, 17.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 136.

- None of the author's names are inverted.
 - When there are more than six authors, one should only reference the first author and then use "et al."
 - Only the first listed author's name is in inverted order; names of additional authors follow but are inverted.**⁸
9. **How is a quotation within a quotation written in American English with regards to quote marks?**
- The quotation starts with inverted commas; the quotation within this quotation is in quotation marks.
 - Quotation marks are used for both.
 - The quotation starts with quotation marks; the quotation within this quotation is put in inverted commas.**⁹
 - Inverted commas are used for both.
10. **When is it not necessary to cite?**
- When the information is common knowledge and can be found in many areas/sources that relate to the topic at hand.**¹⁰
 - When one only summarizes.
 - When one paraphrases a piece of information in one's own words.
 - When the source of a piece of information is anonymous (no author).

⁸ Turabian, 138.

⁹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 35.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 10.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000. A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*. 4th ed. Wilmington, Massachusetts: Great Source Publishing Group, 1999.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 8th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.